

Chemical oscillation

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Chemical oscillation, once thought to be impossible, is now among the most rapidly growing areas of chemical research. This review gives an overview of the field to the newcomer or any one interested in this exciting and fascinating field of nonlinear chemical dynamics. It deals, however, primarily with temporal oscillation in a general way. After a brief history and introduction, the conditions for oscillation and chaos, different oscillating systems (with special reference to the B-Z system and its modifications), and their classification, and mechanisms and models etc. have been discussed.

Introduction

Oscillating chemical reactions¹ are those in which the concentrations of some intermediates oscillate, i.e. their concentrations rise and fall periodically. The concentrations of reactants decrease, the concentrations of products increase, but the concentrations of some intermediates or catalyst species undergo oscillations,

For the chemist, the oscillating reaction is the best example of self-organization. About thirty years ago most chemists were unfamiliar with such reactions. As mechanical (e.g. pendulum) and electrical oscillators often oscillate through their ultimate equilibrium positions and as such oscillation is absolutely forbidden in chemical systems (as it would involve oscillation in free energy), many chemists assumed that chemical oscillations were impossible. Some believed that the reported oscillations were an artifact of heterogeneous phenomena such as bubble formation or were due to the influence of dust particles etc. Most viewed such behavior as a form of perpetual motion, rendered impossible by the second law of thermodynamics. But the situation is entirely different today. Chemical and biochemical oscillations and the more encompassing field of nonlinear chemical dynamics belong to the most interesting and widely studied topics at present.

Prigogine *et al.*^{1r,s,w} first realized that oscillations were possible in some chemical systems provided they were far away from equilibrium. A system could organize (decrease its entropy) as long as the net entropy change in the universe was positive ($\Delta S_{\text{total}} > 0$). Thus the concentrations of the intermediates in a reaction can oscillate with time while

the free energy monotonically decreases. In other words, the decrease in entropy caused by the periodic concentration changes is more than compensated by an entropy increase from other processes (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. (a) Oscillations around equilibrium; inconsistent with the second law (b) Oscillations on the way to equilibrium; free energy decreases monotonically, consistent with the second law.

It has been established that certain thermodynamic and kinetic conditions must be fulfilled for the periodic behavior to occur. The reactions may be studied in various ways, e.g. visually from sharp colour changes, potentiometrically from potential changes (using a platinum electrode or an ion-selective electrode like bromide ion-selective electrode and a reference electrode like calomel electrode), amperometrically from current changes, spectrophotometrically from change in absorption, thermometrically from change in temperature² (or calorimetrically from heat change), pH-metrically from change in pH etc. Recently, nuclear magnetic resonance^{3a} (NMR), as also magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)^{3b} and electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR)^{3c-f} studies of oscillating systems have been made. Obviously all methods are not applicable to all reactions. Generally, the oscillations start after an induction period and the oscillation period may be a few seconds or a few minutes.

Recipe for demonstration : If one adds 10 ml of ~2–3 M H_2SO_4 to about 0.12 g gallic acid and then adds 1–2 drops of ferroin indicator and finally adds 10 ml of KBrO_3 solution (~0.2 M) and shakes the reaction mixture gently, oscillation starts after an induction period of about 5 min. Excellent visible oscillation takes place between orange-red and bluish green colour (time period ~2 min).

The history of oscillations in chemical systems is long. The first example, a gas phase system, was discovered in 1828^{4a}. The first established oscillating chemical reaction in a homogeneous liquid phase system was the iodate-catalyzed decomposition of hydrogen peroxide reported by Bray^{5a} in 1921. The rate of oxygen production and concentration of iodine in the solution changed periodically. But the matter went unnoticed. Later, the reaction was studied extensively by Liebhafsky and goes by the name Bray-Liebhafsky (B-L) reaction.

Interest in chemical oscillation was created primarily by the accidental discovery of a highly impressive reproducible periodic reaction by Belousov^{1a,6a} in 1958. On attempting to oxidise citric acid by bromate in presence of Ce^{4+} ion, he noticed that the yellow colour of the ion in the homogeneous reaction mixture vanished and reappeared in a constant rhythm. He reported that a more distinct change in colour was observed when ferroin (ferrous *o*-phenanthroline) was used as a redox indicator. The solution was blue in an oxidizing solution (corresponding to Ce^{4+} ions) and red in a reducing solution (corresponding to Ce^{3+} ions). He also observed travelling waves in the system. This observation also went unnoticed because it was published in an obscure journal. Zhabotinskii^{6b} modified the reaction by replacing citric acid with malonic acid and obtained a better formulation, which did not produce precipitate. He recognised the importance of the reaction for the understanding of periodic chemical and biological processes, presented his work in Prague conference (1968)⁴² and thus drew the attention of a greater community. That is why this reaction is known as Belousov-Zhabotinskii (B-Z) reaction.

Briggs and Rauscher^{7a} discovered the most dramatic oscillating reaction (B-R reaction) by mixing some components of B-L and B-Z reactions, i.e. by mixing acidic iodate, hydrogen peroxide, manganous salt, an organic substrate like malonic acid and starch. The colour change was from colourless to yellow to blue-black.

Uncatalyzed⁸ bromate oscillators (UBO), where derivatives of phenol and aniline were mostly used as substrates, were reported in the late seventies. These substrates are easily brominated and the main oxidation products are quinones

and quinone imines. Both the catalyzed and uncatalyzed bromate oscillators are sensitive to perturbations, i.e. to addition of certain reagents like halide ions, silver, thallium(III), mercury(II) ions, etc.

Many other systems⁹ like permanganate system, chlorite-iodide system, iodate-arsenous acid system etc. show oscillatory behavior, but B-Z reaction has been studied most extensively. Different variations of the organic substrate, acid and catalyst have been made. Most of the chemical oscillators have been systematically designed^{10a} now after the conditions that were necessary for, or conducive to oscillations were established.

Chemical oscillation may be temporal or spatial. The former is observed in a stirred solution (e.g. stirred by a magnetic stirrer). The latter, which is a propagation of waves, takes place in an unstirred solution. Alternate horizontal stripes of oxidized and reduced forms of the indicator appear and propagate themselves through the solution. Again chemical oscillation may be periodic (simple as also complex type) or aperiodic (chaos).

Chemical oscillations are generally of relaxation type. Almost discontinuous transitions between distinguishable states occur. Each of these states persists for a significant time between the transitions. Thus in B-Z reaction, which is a bromide ion controlled reaction, the behavior of an electrode specific to bromide ion (Br^- ion sensitive electrode) can be followed (Fig. 2). The state is reduced between points E and F when $[\text{Br}^-]$ is relatively high and the state is oxidized between points G and H when $[\text{Br}^-]$ is relatively low. Rapid transitions between clearly defined oxidized and reduced states take place. A platinum electrode is often used to serve as a redox electrode as the potential is a function of the $\text{M}^{(n+1)+}/\text{M}^{n+}$ concentration ratio.

Oscillating reactions may be studied either in the batch mode or CSTR mode. In batch mode, the system has a fixed supply of reactants and it is thermodynamically closed. The

Fig. 2. Potentiometric traces; initial concentrations : $[\text{CH}_2(\text{COOH})_2]_0 = 0.13 \text{ M}$, $[\text{KBrO}_3]_0 = 0.063 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Ce}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{NO}_3)_6]_0 = 0.005 \text{ M}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_0 = 0.8 \text{ M}$.

oscillations are damped after some time and time period increases after a while. The CSTR mode (continuous flow stirred tank reactor) was first adopted by Pacault^{11a}. There is a continuous supply of reactants and the system is thermodynamically open. The oscillations are sustained and can go on for an infinite time.

Requirements for chemical oscillation (thermodynamic and kinetic)

(i) The system must be far from equilibrium, i.e. ΔG for the overall reaction must be large and negative – only thermodynamic requirement. This requirement is met by using CSTR or studying the initial stage of the reaction in a closed system, i.e. when it is far from equilibrium. A reacting system at, or close to a stable equilibrium will not oscillate.

(ii) Nonlinearity : The mass-action dynamic law of the reaction must be nonlinear. This means that it contains terms that are the product of two or more intermediate concentrations or the concentration of one intermediate raised to a power greater than one – minimum kinetic requirement.

(iii) Feedback : Some product of a step in the reaction sequence must exert an influence on its own rate of formation. Usually nonlinearities related to autocatalysis, self-inhibition or a delayed feedback loop are required. A reaction mechanism must have an autocatalytic step (positive feedback) and a step that produces a species that inhibits (negative feedback) the autocatalysis. The inhibitory step thus provides the feedback that controls the nonlinear (autocatalytic) step.

(iv) Bistability : The system must be able to exist in two stable steady states for the same values of the externally controlled conditions (constraints). Bistability (Fig. 3) is characteristic of most oscillating reactions in CSTR mode but not explicitly in batch mode.

By a steady state is meant a condition of the system in which all the variables, such as the concentration of each

Fig. 3. Bistability by a mechanical analogy (a ball rolling in a potential well) : A and B, stable steady states; C, unstable steady state.

chemical species, have attained constant values. The steady state is stable if it can adjust to a small change in a variable and recover without being transformed into a new state. The stability of a state can be evaluated by means of a linear stability analysis^{1x}, a standard mathematical technique which begins by calculating the pertinent concentrations for the state concerned.

Closed and open systems¹²

Early studies on chemical oscillation were carried out in thermodynamically closed (batch) configuration. No chemicals enter or leave the system once the reaction begins. Many reactions are still carried out or occur naturally in such systems. Batch reactors are convenient for lecture demonstrations and for studying the basic kinetics of a system. Once a closed system has been assembled with specific initial concentrations, pressure and temperature etc. there is a uniquely specified corresponding chemical equilibrium state. The monotonic approach to equilibrium does not, however, rule out chemical oscillation in the initial state when it is far from equilibrium. When systems exchange mass with their surroundings, and hence are thermodynamically open, the inflow and outflow means that the individual molecules spend only a finite time in the reactor. The simplest example of an open system is the CSTR developed by Pacault^{11a}. This was a key experimental development in the study of complex dynamical phenomena. A flux of reactant chemicals is introduced at a constant rate and a flux of well-mixed reactor contents is removed at the same rate. More complex examples include living things and atmosphere. The use of open reactors overcomes many of the disadvantages of studying reactions in thermodynamically closed vessels. A system that oscillates under batch conditions will nearly always oscillate under continuous flow, but the converse is rarely true.

In a CSTR, the molecules spend only a finite time (residence time τ) in the reactor because of the continuous flow. So the reaction does not approach the chemical equilibrium and the system remains far from equilibrium. In some cases, more than one steady state may coexist. Oscillations may occur and last forever. Apparently simple chemical systems may give rise to a remarkable variety of dynamical phenomena like multiple stationary states, simple and complex periodic oscillations, aperiodic oscillation (chaos) and the growth of travelling waves and spatial structures in initially homogeneous media. In a CSTR, the variables or constraints under control are : (a) temperature of the external bath, (b) concentrations of the input chemicals in the reservoirs and (c) flow rate through the pump or equivalently the average

residence time of material in the reactor, τ . The reciprocal of the residence time $K_0 (=1/\tau)$ is given by $K_0 = F/V$, where F is the flow rate (ml s^{-1}) and V the reactor volume in ml. For moderate flow rates, the reaction exhibits large amplitude oscillations very similar to those observed in closed systems. At very high flow rates, the corresponding very short residence times will be insufficient for much reaction to occur. With very low flow rates, the residence time becomes very long and the system has time to approach the chemical equilibrium.

CSTR has a central role in the systematic design of chemical oscillators. The first successful design^{10a} (arsenite-iodate-chlorite system) has been followed by the addition of dozens of new systems. The existence of simple models for chemical oscillator has played a major role in inspiring and in guiding these advances. The plan for designing a chemical oscillator included four steps^{10b}: (a) finding an autocatalytic system, (b) running the reaction in a CSTR, (c) varying the conditions until a region of bistability is found and (d) introducing another substance capable of affecting the two branches of bistability differently and thereby of inducing oscillations.

A homogeneous oscillatory chemical reaction in a closed system is described by a set of ordinary differential equations,

$$\frac{dx_i}{dt} = F_i(x_1, \dots, x_n), i = 1, \dots, n$$

one for each of the species. The equations are obtained from a reaction mechanism consisting of elementary steps by use of mass action kinetics. In an open system (CSTR) terms are added for inflows and outflows, giving

$$F_i(x_1, \dots, x_n) = R_i(x_1, \dots, x_n) + K_0(x_i^0 - x_i)$$

where $R_i(x_1, \dots, x_n)$ is the set of reaction terms for the i -th species and $K_0(x_i^0 - x_i)$ is the term due to inflow and outflow of the i -th species; K_0 is the reciprocal of the residence time and x_i^0 is the input concentration of the i -th species. In 'semibatch' reactors^{11b}, there is a continuous inflow of reactants into the reactor, but no outflow is provided. These reactors have characteristics intermediate between those of batch and flow reactors and may be used for testing mechanisms as one can vary which species are placed in the reactor and which are flowed in. For studying chemical waves, Swinney and coworkers^{11c} developed the continuously fed unstirred reactor (CFUR), which has been modified by Dutt *et al.*^{11d}. One recent development is the differential flow reactor, devised originally by Rovinsky and Menzinger^{11e} and investigated by other workers^{11f}. The basic idea behind this reactor is that the reacting species flow through it at different rates.

Excitability^{12b}

An excitable system is characterized by having a stable steady state and so is not spontaneously oscillatory. With slightly large perturbations, the system is stimulated into a single excursion, with a colour change and back and a single large peak in the intermediate concentrations, similar to a single oscillation.

Chaos^{12,13}

Chaos has widespread appearance in many fields including biology, chemistry, physics, economics, engineering and medicine. Chemical chaos refers to the behavior of a reaction in which the concentrations neither attain constant values nor oscillate periodically but increase and decrease in an apparently random and unpredictable way. It represents an inherently complex phenomenon. At least three independent first order differential equations are required to generate chaos whereas two equations will suffice for periodic oscillation and one for bistability. Chaotic behavior results when inaccuracies or uncertainties in the starting conditions grow exponentially with time. Consequently, the state of the system shortly becomes totally unpredictable. All that is required for a system to be potentially chaotic are one or more nonlinear coupling terms in the equations of motion and more than two phase-space dimensions. The type of chaos that stems from the structure of well-defined nonlinear differential equations is called deterministic chaos, for the behavior of the solutions is predictable but infinitely sensitive to the initial conditions.

There are several ways in which a reaction can be steered into a chaotic regime. Thus in certain systems, the change in a parameter such as a flow rate through the reaction vessel or the rate of stirring may result in successive doubling of the period of the limit cycle. As each period doubles, the periodicity of the motion becomes less apparent and finally appears like random fluctuations. The trajectory of the composition of the system is now highly complex and may take a path that never retraces its path or crosses itself. Such a path is called a strange attractor. Our inability to predict the composition of a system that is in a chaotic regime, stems from our inability experimentally to know the initial conditions exactly or make a later determination of the composition at an exact later instant. Chaos in the oscillatory B-Z reaction is exclusively studied in open flow systems and interpreted as deterministic. Ruoff^{13d} has shown experimentally the occurrence of chaotic oscillations in batch B-Z systems and their simulations by incorporating concentration fluctuation (related to stirring process) in the original Oregonator model.

Limit cycle, stability and bifurcation^{1q}

A limit cycle is a closed, 1-D curve embedded in phase space, which represents periodic oscillations. For a limit cycle to exist, the chemical mechanism should have at least one autocatalytic stage and a negative feedback. Autocatalysis provides the accelerating growth of one species, and the negative feedback terminates the autocatalytic explosion. In oscillations this sequence repeats periodically.

Stable limit cycles and stable steady states are also termed attractors, because of the feature of attracting the trajectories in the phase plane. For a closed system equilibrium is always the ultimate attractor. More complex dynamics is possible in systems with three or more variables including strange attractors (chaotic attractor) and the associated phenomenon of deterministic chaos. Strange attractors are geometrical objects with dimension that is strangely non-integer. An attractor may lose its stability suddenly when a control parameter is changed, i.e. bifurcation occurs. A response diagram represents the dynamic response as a function of the control parameter.

Modes of representation of data^{1x}

(i) *Time series* : A plot of signal vs time is known as a time series. This first approach is most common and may yield valuable information. Some function of concentration like electrode potential or absorbance is measured as a function of time at one set of constraints.

(ii) *Constraint-response plot (or bifurcation diagram)* : Here a particular response is plotted against a constraint parameter like flow rate. One comes to know how the responses of the system such as the period and amplitude of the oscillation vary with the control parameter.

(iii) *Phase diagrams* : The results of many time series can be shown on a plot whose axes are the two constraint variables of interest. Each point on the plot indicates the kind of state, i.e. steady, oscillatory or chaotic at a particular set of parameters.

(iv) *Phase portraits* : At a fixed set of constraints, i.e. initial concentration, flow rate and temperature, two or three dependent (concentration) variables are plotted to get a picture of the system's path through the phase space, e.g. plot of Pt-electrode potential vs bromide electrode potential in the B-Z reaction.

Mechanisms and models^{1x,12b}

Chemists want to understand the chemical reactions on the molecular level and a mechanism is a map of these processes. A mechanism is a series of elementary reactions that

involve actual molecular collisions that lead to transformation. Mechanisms typically aim for a semiquantitative match to a particular reaction; models are often deliberately simpler and attempt to catch the main qualitative features of a broader class of reactions.

Major types of chemical oscillators

The major types of chemical oscillators are oxyhalogen oscillators and are grouped into three main families : (A) Bromate oscillators, e.g. original B-Z reaction and its many variants, (B) iodate oscillators, e.g. B-L and B-R reactions, (C) chlorite oscillators, e.g. arsenite-iodate-chlorite system.

(A) *Bromate oscillators – Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction (B-Z reaction)* :

The classical^{1a} B-Z reaction consists of the oxidation by bromate ion in an acidic medium of easily brominated organic material, catalyzed by weak one-electron metal-ion oxidants. There are many variants of the B-Z reaction and uncatalyzed oscillations are also possible. The reaction is usually carried out in sulfuric acid (approx. 1 M). There is, however, an absolute requirement for bromate ion. Under various conditions the B-Z reaction behaves in a variety of startling ways. Most famous are the sustained temporal oscillations in oxidation state of the transitional metal ion (easily observed as colour changes) and the waves of oxidation that propagate periodically through the unstirred layers of the reagent. In a CSTR, the B-Z reaction also exhibits (a) bistability^{14a-c}, i.e. two stable steady states between which the system can be flipped by suitable perturbations, (b) burst of oscillations^{14a,b,d} in which nearly identical pulses of several cycles of oscillations are separated by more or less regular periods of quiescence and (c) irregular patterns^{14e,f,g}, such as quasi-periodic and chaotic oscillations. The complex temporal and spatial phenomena have caused a flurry of activity among chemists, mathematicians, biologists and physicists.

Chemical requirements for the major components in a B-Z system^{1q} :

(i) *Organic substrate* : (a) Should react slowly with bromate in absence of a catalyst, and (b) should be both brominable and oxidisable.

(ii) *Catalyst* : It should be a one-electron redox couple with a standard reduction potential between 1.0 and 1.5 V (e.g. $\text{Ce}^{4+}/\text{Ce}^{3+}$, $\text{Mn}^{3+}/\text{Mn}^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{3+}/\text{Fe}(\text{phen})_3^{2+}$).

(iii) *Oxidizing agent* : Bromate is very useful, since depending on the chemical conditions, it can participate either in two-electron (oxygen transfer) reactions or in one-electron reactions,

Basic mechanism and model for B-Z reaction :

The mechanism for B-Z reaction was proposed by Field, Körös and Noyes (FKN)^{15a} in their landmark papers in 1972 and accepted universally. Though the FKN mechanism (involving 18 elementary steps and some 20 different chemical species) which was confirmed by computer simulation by Edelson *et al.*^{15b}, has been modified, refined and extended over the years, it is still widely accepted as correct and complete in major respects.

The overall chemical reaction in B-Z system using malonic acid as organic substrate may be written in terms of only stoichiometrically significant species as follows :

The FKN mechanism may be discussed^{15c} in terms of processes A (a non-radical set) and B (a radical set), coupled by a third set, called process C. The last process allows control of the reacting system to be alternately passed back and forth between processes A and B.

Process A :

The reaction of Br^- with BrO_3^- to yield Br_2 which reacts with malonic acid to generate bromomalonic acid,

Process B :

Autocatalytic formation of bromous acid with a rapid oxidation of Ce^{III} to Ce^{IV} ,

Process C (A recovery process) :

Alternatively,

where f is a stoichiometric factor.

Process-A removes Br^- ion, Process-B provides the autocatalysis and Process-C produces Br^- ion and metal ion in lower oxidation state. Processes A and B together represents a sort of bistability. Three distinct intermediates undergo coupled oscillations. Bromous acid (HBrO_2) is the switched intermediate, bromide ion is the control intermediate and Ce^{IV} is the regeneration intermediate.

When $[\text{Br}^-]$ is high, $[\text{HBrO}_2]$ and $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ are small, the system is in a reduced state and Process-A is dominant. When $[\text{Br}^-]$ is small, $[\text{HBrO}_2]$ and $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ are large, the system is in an oxidized state and Process-B is dominant. Process-A leads inevitably to Process-B by the consumption of Br^- ions. For oscillation to occur a way must exist to turn off Process-B, i.e. to return control to Process-A and to reset the system by reducing Ce^{IV} back to Ce^{III} . This is done by Process-C, whose function is to, after a delay while Ce^{IV} and HOBr accumulate, poison Process-B by the production of Br^- from products of Process-B. This completes a delayed negative feedback loop. Process-C also reduces Ce^{IV} back to Ce^{3+} to reinitialize Process-B for the next oscillation. Bromide ion is the control intermediate whose concentration determines whether Process-A (high $[\text{Br}^-]$) or Process-B (low $[\text{Br}^-]$) is in control. The transition occurs near a critical value of $[\text{Br}^-]$. Whenever $[\text{Br}^-]$ passes through $[\text{Br}^-]_{\text{crit}}$, $[\text{HBrO}_2]$ changes almost discontinuously. It is this almost discontinuous change in $[\text{HBrO}_2]$ that generates the relaxation oscillations. In many cases a critical amount of bromomalonic acid must accumulate before oscillation begins. This is apparently the source of the induction period before the onset of oscillation. The induction period can be nearly eliminated if it is added initially.

The stoichiometric factor f represents the number of bromide ions produced as two Ce^{IV} ions are reduced. The condition for oscillation is given by $1/2 < f < 1 + \sqrt{2}$.

Oscillations are suppressed if f is either too large or too small. A balance between the efficiency of Process-C and the rates of Processes A and B must be achieved. If f is too small, the system settles to a steady state corresponding to

the oxidized form of the catalyst and low bromide ion concentration. If f is too large, the buildup of bromide inhibits the autocatalysis and oxidation in Process-B and a reduced steady state is established. B-Z systems which show excitability have values for f slightly above the maximum for oscillation. Sirimungkala *et al.*^{15d} pointed out recently on the basis of their kinetic studies on bromination, that the possibility of bromide production in the reaction of malonic acid or bromomalonic acid with hypobromous acid can be ruled out. These results are important for the negative feedback loop in the B-Z reaction.

Various models like Lotka model^{16a}, Brusselator model^{16b}, Oregonator model^{17a} etc. have been proposed for oscillators. The Oregonator model (after Oregon, USA, where it was developed) was developed by Field and Noyes to illustrate the FKN mechanism of B-Z oscillatory reaction. It reproduces many but not all features of the full chemistry. There are five irreversible steps 01 to 05 in the model,

Process-A

Process-B

Process-C

$A \equiv \text{BrO}_3^-$, $X \equiv \text{HBrO}_2$, $Y \equiv \text{Br}^-$, $Z \equiv 2 \text{Ce}^{4+}$, $P \equiv \text{HOBr}$ and f is a stoichiometric factor.

The dynamic behavior of the Oregonator model is described by the following differential equations :

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = K_{01}AY - K_{02}XY + K_{03}AX - 2 K_{04}X^2$$

$$\frac{dY}{dt} = fK_{05}Z - (K_{01}A + K_{02}X)Y$$

$$\frac{dZ}{dt} = K_{03}AX - K_{05}Z$$

It can be shown that when Y ($\equiv \text{Br}^-$) is large, X ($\equiv \text{HBrO}_2$) is small, and when Y is small, X is large. Whenever Y passes through $Y_{\text{critical}} (= K_{03}A/K_{02})$, X changes almost discontinuously generating the relaxation oscillations.

Modifications^{1b} of the classic B-Z reaction :

Modifications of the B-Z reaction can be minor (such as substitution for one of the reactants of an essentially equiva-

lent material) or major. There are several severely modified systems whose relationship to the classic B-Z reaction and the FKN mechanism was not initially clear. They are, however, all driven by bromate and they fall into 3 classes : (a) bromine-hydrolysis-controlled (BHC), (b) non-bromide ion controlled (NBC) and (c) uncatalyzed bromate oscillators (UBO).

(i) *BHC oscillators¹⁸* : In some systems, Br^- production via Process-C is not possible either because there is no brominated species equivalent to BrMA (bromomalonic acid) formed or because the brominated species that are formed do not react with the oxidized form of the metal-ion catalyst to yield Br^- . Oscillations may still appear in such a system if the Br_2 formed in Processes A and B reaches a high enough concentration. The Br^- required to shift control of the system from Process-B to Process-A in these cases comes from the hydrolysis of Br_2 (and hence the name),

There must be, however, species or processes to reduce the oxidized form of the metal-ion catalyst and to remove the Br_2 . The best known BHC oscillator is the heterogeneous Ce^{3+} - BrO_3^- -oxalic acid system discovered by Noszticzius and Bodiss. The main characteristics of the BHC oscillators are : (a) the absence of an organic compound easily brominated and the lack of a brominated organic compound that can be readily oxidized by the metallic ion, (b) the control of bromide ion concentration by the hydrolysis of molecular Br_2 , not by the oxidation of organic compounds, and (c) the absence of an induction period, as the most important feature; Field and Boyd proposed a detailed mechanism. Zhang and Field, Rastogi and Misra, Berenstein *et al.*, Guedes and Faria and others have done important work on BHC oscillation.

(ii) *NBC oscillators¹⁹* : There are some systems which show oscillations in colour and/or redox potential, but not in $[\text{Br}^-]$. Noszticzius first observed such oscillations in malonic acid in the presence of Ag^+ , which maintains $[\text{Br}^-]$ at a very low level while AgBr precipitates out. An induction period is necessary after the Ag^+ is consumed before normal oscillation resumes. Körös *et al.* reported that NBC oscillations appear when Ag^+ is added to the heterogeneous oxalic acid oscillator and to uncatalyzed oscillators. It is difficult to rationalize NBC oscillations within the FKN framework.

(iii) *UBO oscillators⁸* : Körös and Orban^{8a} found that with gallic acid Br^- - controlled oscillations occurred even in the absence of metal ions. A large number of substrates which were phenol and aniline derivatives showed

uncatalyzed oscillations^{8b}. The substrates used by other authors were mostly similar aromatic compounds, such as aryldiazonium salts, aminophenols and their derivatives. In general, fewer oscillations appear in uncatalyzed than in catalyzed systems. Oscillations can be restarted if Ce or Mn ion is added soon after the uncatalyzed oscillations cease.

The oscillatory behavior of uncatalyzed bromate oscillators has been explained in terms of OKN mechanism^{8c} (a modification of FKN mechanism). Numerical simulations based on this mechanism by Herbine and Field^{8d} reproduced the main features of uncatalyzed oscillations. Process-B is modified in this mechanism by the replacement of the reaction: $\text{BrO}_2^* + \text{Ce}^{3+} + \text{H}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Ce}^{4+} + \text{HBrO}_2$, the metal-ion oxidation by BrO_2^* , by

Extended models were suggested by Liu and Scott²² and by Györgi *et al.*²⁸. A quinone derivative of the original organic reactant like gallic acid plays the role of the metal catalyst.

Uncatalyzed oscillators are mechanistically simpler than catalyzed oscillators. They are not complicated either by the coordination chemistry of the metal-ion catalyst or by degradation of the organic material to CO_2 .

Other^{1b} modifications of the B-Z reaction :

(i) *Inorganic acid substitution* : Cerium ion catalyzed systems are most sensitive to such substitutions, as it is only in about 1M H_2SO_4 that BrO_3^- has the potential to oxidise Ce^{III} to Ce^{IV} . The manganese catalyzed system has been run in H_3PO_4 and HClO_4 . Uncatalyzed oscillators have been run in HNO_3 , HClO_4 , H_3PO_4 , CCl_3COOH and H_2SO_4 . HCl cannot be used because of the inhibitory effect of Cl^- ions.

(ii) *Metal-ion catalyst substitution* : The catalyst must have two stable oxidation states separated by a single electron and a potential of 1–1.5 V if it operates according to FKN mechanism. Metal ions and metal-ion complexes used as catalysts include Ce^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , $\text{Fe}(\text{phenan})_3^{2+}$, $\text{Fe}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$, $\text{Ru}(\text{phenan})_3^{2+}$, $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$, $\text{Ce}^{3+} + \text{V}^{5+}$, $\text{Ce}^{4+} + \text{Fe}(\text{phenan})_3^{2+}$ (mixed catalyst), bis-pyridine Ag complexes etc. There are differences in the behavior of oscillators using various catalysts. Induction period is not always shown. Actually electron-transfer reactions occur with Ce and Mn ions by an inner-sphere mechanism and with the complexes by an outer-sphere mechanism. Copper and nickel macrocyclic complexes²⁰ (e.g. $[\text{Ni}(\text{TIM})]^{2+}$, where TIM is 2,3,9,10-tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetra-azacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetrane macrocyclic ligand) and chromium complex $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{OH})(\text{bpy})_4]^{3+}$ have also been used as catalysts.

(iii) *Substitution of organic materials* : A large number of organic substrates (citric acid, malonic acid, bromomalonic acid, malic acid etc.) has been used, gallic acid²² being very popular. Some fall into the class of easily brominated dicarboxylic acids and the mechanism in these cases is apparently similar to that with malonic acid (MA). Some organic substrates lead to very different reactions and some others fall into intermediate regions. Most interesting results have been obtained with ketones (like cyclohexanone) and diketones (like 2,4-pentanedione, AA). Mixed substrates have often been used. In the presence of a mixture of MA, AA and EA in a Mn-catalyzed system, sequential types of oscillation have been observed corresponding to each of the three substrates. Sequential oscillation has also been observed by other workers²³ with other substrates like vanillin²⁴. Carbohydrates^{25a,b} have also been used as substrates. Surfactant (e.g. Triton X-100)-induced^{25a} carbohydrate chemical oscillation has been reported by Zhanbo *et al.* Hexing and Haihan^{25c} reported oscillations with glycine and other amino acids. Oscillations involving L-glutamine were reported by Huihao^{25d}. The oscillatory behavior of B-Z reverse micelle system^{25e} has also been studied. A triglyceride hydrolysis oscillator^{25f} (water in oil emulsion system) has been recently reported.

Some important studies and observations on B-Z systems :

(i) B-Z reaction may show dependence on the method of mixing of the reagents. A mixture of high and low amplitude oscillations has been observed with a high stirring rate whereas a regime of high amplitude oscillations is followed by a sequence of low amplitude ones with a low stirring rate. Such mixed mode^{26a,b} oscillation is the most commonly occurring form of complex oscillation. Moreover, the number of oscillations is small when the stirring rate is high.

(ii) Temperature triggered^{26c} chemical oscillation has been observed in some uncatalyzed bromate oscillators with *para*-substituted phenols as the organic substrate. When perturbed with chloride ions, a sudden transition occurs at a well-defined threshold temperature from the non-oscillatory to the oscillatory state, and back.

(iii) Considering chemical oscillation as a monomolecular process^{26d-h} and using the reciprocal of the time period at initial concentrations as a first order rate constant (K), the apparent energy of activation (E_a) of the oscillation can be evaluated (using Arrhenius equation, $K = A \exp(-E_a/RT)$) from the slope of the straight line plot of $\log K$ vs $1/T$. Similarly, a plot of $\log(K/T)$ vs $1/T$ (using logarithmic form of Eyring equation) gives a straight line, the slope and in-

tercept of which give the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger).

(iv) The effects of addition of D(+)-glucose^{27a} (a typical reducing agent), acetone^{26h,27b,c}, ethano^{27b}, halide ions^{6b,15a,18,28} (depends on the nature of the halide) and sulfate and perchlorate ions²⁹ have been studied. In a recent work^{27d} glucose has been used as a substrate also. Perturbation by UV, visible and ⁶⁰Co γ -radiation^{1b} has also been studied. The effects of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)^{27e} and noionic surfactants^{27f} on B-Z system have been reported recently.

(v) Inorganic B-Z type oscillations have been periodically observed^{30a,b}. An absolutely homogeneous inorganic B-Z type oscillator^{30c} has been reported in the system BrO_3^- - H_2PO_2^- - Mn^{2+} - $\text{Fe}(\text{phenan})_3^{2+}$ - H_2SO_4 in a batch reactor.

(vi) Mixed aquo-organic media have been used by many workers (Lalitha *et al.*²⁴, Biswas *et al.*²).

Other mechanisms and models for B-Z reaction :

(i) *Generalized mechanism* : After the formulation of the bromide ion controlled FKN mechanism^{15a} and Oregonator model^{17a} for catalyzed B-Z reactions and OKN mechanism^{8c} for uncatalyzed reactions, Noyes proposed a generalized mechanism^{15c} for different classes of known (batch) bromate-driven oscillators and this served to unify the field and to point out areas of further research. The simplest hypothesis^{15f} on the mechanism of these reactions is that the dynamic features of the system are defined by the kinetics of the reaction (1), (i.e. autocatalytic reaction of Ce^{3+} oxidation by bromate), while reaction (2) (i.e. reduction of Ce^{4+}) provides only a linear feedback,

Br^- formed in reaction (2) is a strong inhibitor of reaction (1). The Br^- ion interacts with some active intermediate of reaction (1) and thus disappears from the system at some rate. When $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ decreasing due to reaction (2) reaches a lower threshold, $[\text{Br}^-]$ drops sharply. Reaction (1) then starts at a high rate and as a result $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ increases. When $[\text{Ce}^{4+}]$ reaches an upper threshold, $[\text{Br}^-]$ increases sharply and reaction (1) is blocked. The cycle is then repeated.

(ii) *Explodator, revised Oregonator, radicalator and modified Oregonator* : An explodator^{31a} (NFS; treats Br_2 rather than Br^- ion as influencing the dynamic behavior), a

revised Oregonator^{17b,c} (six irreversible steps in place of five; final oxidation state of bromine is +1, 0, -1), a radicalator^{31b} (malonic acid radical MA^\cdot considered as control intermediate), a modified radicalator^{31c} (concluding that Br^- ion control cannot be completely replaced by MA^\cdot control) and a modified Oregonator^{17d} (for photoinduced behavior in $\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3^{2+}$ -catalyzed B-Z reaction) have been proposed.

(iii) *GTF model* : The reduced skeleton model of FKN mechanism, i.e. the Oregonator treats the oxybromine chemistry (inorganic part) in some detail but lumps the organic part together into a single overall reaction by using chemical intuition based on the mechanism, $2 \text{Ce}^{4+} \rightarrow f \text{Br}^-$. Edelson *et al.*^{31d} suggested a model which dealt with the elementary reactions of the B-Z organic chemistry. The model, however, suffered from certain limitations. An 80-reaction 26-species mechanistic model (Györgyi, Turanyi and Field^{31e}, GTF) represents a significant step forward in understanding the chemistry of the B-Z reaction. There are 14 reactions in the inorganic subset and 66 reactions in the organic subset. The latter contains 4 types of reactions : (a) reactions not consuming or producing radicals, (b) reactions producing radicals, (c) reactions consuming radicals and (d) reactions preserving radicals. Modified values of rate constants were taken. This model is perhaps the most complete representation of the chemistry of the complex B-Z system. A simplification^{31f} of the model and some suggestions^{3d,31g} on the model have been made. A simple model has been proposed later^{31h,i} for a qualitative description of transient and asymptotic B-Z oscillations.

(B) Iodate oscillators :

(i) *Bray-Liebhaftsky reaction (B-L reaction)* : Bray^{5a} observed oscillations in iodine concentration during the iodate-catalyzed disproportionation of H_2O_2 in acidic solution ($2 \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2$). The solution became alternately yellow and colourless. The reaction was extensively studied by Liebhaftsky^{5b} through long years. A detailed molecular mechanism was proposed by Sharma and Noyes^{5c}. Different groups disagree seriously about the mechanistic explanations. This light-sensitive reaction is inhibited by very rapid stirring. The frequency can also be slowed greatly by sonication. These observations are regarded as unequivocal evidence that rapid removal of oxygen can suppress oscillations. A skeleton mechanism was proposed by Treindl and Noyes^{5d}. It is generally recognised that oscillations in both I_2 and I^- concentrations result from the alternating dominance of the oxidation and reduction of H_2O_2 by IO_3^- to I_2 and by I_2 back to IO_3^- respectively. The mechanism has

been used by Noyes *et al.*^{5c} to develop a mathematical model of this system based on only two concentration variables, $[I_2]$ and $[O_2]$ and three composition parameters. Sevcik and Adamcikova^{5f} suggested that the rate of transport of volatile iodine from the B-L solution to the gas phase might be a significant component of the overall mechanism of the B-L oscillations. A complete elucidation of the mechanism of the overall reaction, however, is still awaited.

(ii) *Briggs-Rauscher reaction (B-R reaction)* : The most spectacular and dramatic of the relaxation oscillators driven by oxyhalogen species was discovered by Briggs and Rauscher^{7a} by mixing components from the B-L and B-Z reactions. B-R reaction is thus a hybrid of B-L and B-Z reactions. The necessary species are acidic iodate, hydrogen peroxide, a manganous salt and an organic substrate like malonic acid^{7a}, acetoacetic ester^{7b} etc. Starch is used as an indicator for enhancing the colour due to I_3^- . The colour change is from gold to blue to colourless and back to gold. The overall stoichiometric change can be described as

The reaction exhibits a far richer collection of nonlinear dynamic phenomena than simple oscillation. In a flow reactor, complex oscillations as well as multiple steady states accompanied by a variety of bifurcation and hysteresis phenomena have been observed. Regarding the mechanism of the reaction, virtually identical conclusions were reached independently by Noyes and Furrow^{7c} and by De Kepper and Epstein^{7d}, and it is held that the essential features of the mechanism have been elucidated⁹.

(C) Chlorite oscillators :

The report of the first chlorite oscillator (the arsenite-iodate-chlorite system in CSTR) by De Kepper *et al.*^{10a} is also the first report of a systematically designed homogeneous oscillating reaction. The spectrophotometric absorption at 460 nm (where both I_3^- and I_2 absorb significantly) and the potential of an iodide-sensitive electrode were followed as a function of time. Two autocatalytic subsystems, arsenite-iodate and chlorite-iodide were linked together in a CSTR to give rise to oscillation. Dateo *et al.*^{10c} studied the reaction between chlorite and iodide in acidic solution in a CSTR. The system exhibited bistability, and at high $[ClO_2^-]$ and $[I^-]$, sustained oscillations as well. The key reaction is $ClO_2^- + 4 I^- + 4 H^+ = Cl^- + 2 I_2 + 2 H_2O$. It is autocatalytic in iodine and is inhibited by iodide. The existence of bistability and oscillation in this system is consistent with the 'cross-shaped phase diagram' model of Boissonade and De Kepper. This reaction forms the basis

of an entirely new family of oscillating reactions when chlorite and iodine containing species (I_3^- , I^- or I_2) are combined with a variety of reducing ($Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$, SO_3^{2-} , $S_2O_3^{2-}$) or oxidizing (IO_3^- , $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$, MnO_4^- , BrO_3^-) agents. In addition to oscillations, the system^{10d} containing chlorite, iodide, iodate and arsenite can exhibit three different steady states. This system may be thought of as an arsenite perturbation of the chlorite-iodide-iodate system, as an iodide perturbation of the chlorite-iodate-arsenite oscillator or as a hybrid of the chlorite-iodide and iodate-arsenite bistable subsystems. The chlorite-thiosulfate-iodide-iodine system^{10e} provides another example of coupled chemical oscillator. The chlorite oscillators may be divided into four classes : (i) the fundamental ClO_2^- - I^- (or ClO_2^- - I^- - IO_3^-) oscillator, (ii) ClO_2^- - I^- -oxidant systems, (iii) ClO_2^- - IO_3^- (or I_2) reductant systems, and (iv) iodine-free systems, e.g. ClO_2^- - $S_2O_3^{2-}$. Some chlorite oscillators^{10f} (e.g. chlorite-iodate-thiosulfate) also exhibit batch oscillation. Repeated spatial wave patterns^{10f} (trigger waves) may develop in initially homogeneous unstirred thin layers of ClO_2^- - I^- -malonic acid (CIMA) solutions. This is related to the bromate-bromide-malonic acid (B-Z) reaction by halogen atom substitution.

Epstein and Kustin^{10g} set up a reaction mechanism for the chlorite-iodide oscillator. Citri and Epstein^{10h} revised the mechanism, and Strasser *et al.*¹⁰ⁱ made a detailed analysis of it. Stoichiometric network analysis (SNA) was used to determine the complete set of major reaction pathways (extreme currents) of the mechanism under CSTR conditions. A simplified oscillatory mechanism was extracted which accounted for the oscillatory behavior of the full mechanism.

Minimal oscillator^{32a} :

The concept of a minimal oscillator has been extremely helpful in guiding the design of new chemical oscillators. A minimal oscillator in a family of oscillatory reactions may be defined as the oscillator containing components that are found in all members of the family as reactants or are generated during the reaction, and from which no component can be removed without destroying the ability of the system to oscillate.

Since all permanganate-substrate reactions lead to manganese(II) and the phosphate is essential for oscillation, the Mn^{2+} - MnO_4^- -phosphate system (the Guyard^{32b} reaction) at near neutral pH in a CSTR is the minimal member of the family of MnO_4^- -reductant-phosphate oscillators. If one can identify a minimal oscillator, the system can be often used as a core for building additional members of the family. Thus the BrO_3^- - Br^- - Mn^{2+} minimal bromate oscillator gives rise

to a variety of inorganic bromate oscillators in which bromide ion is replaced by reducing agents that generate Br^- from bromate. Similarly, many oscillators containing chlorite and iodine-containing species can be constructed from the minimal ClO_2^- - I^- system. A tentative classification^{1c} of oxyhalogen oscillators is as follows : Class A = minimal, Class B = minimal + inorganic reductant, Class B' = minimal + organic reductant and Class C = minimal + oxidant. There are, however, interconnections between the classes.

Stoichiometric network analysis (SNA) and operational procedure towards the classification of chemical oscillators^{12c,33a,b}

Stoichiometric network analysis (developed by Clarke^{33a}) is a mathematical method which allows the identification of the basic unstable features of a mechanism. A chemical mechanism constitutes a set of processes (chemical reactions) with rate laws that remove or produce certain entities (chemical species) in fixed ratios which are given by the stoichiometries of the elementary reactions of the model mechanism. Hence such a mechanism constitutes a stoichiometric network and can be analyzed using SNA. A major objective of SNA is to determine what kind of dynamical behavior is possible for a chosen network. SNA provides the potential stability or instability of networks without using any rate constant.

Eiswirth *et al.*^{33b} have used SNA to classify oscillatory reactions according to their basic unstable feature and the type of their dominant negative feedback loop. The species are first categorized into those 'essential' and 'nonessential' for the occurrence of oscillations. Chemical species are 'non-essential' if, on being held constant, oscillations continue. Species are 'essential' for the oscillations if on being held constant, oscillations of all other species are suppressed. The essential species are further divided into subcategories according to their roles in the mechanism. The work attempts a classification of oscillators based not on the details of the chemistry involved but on abstract mechanistic criteria. Altogether 25 abstract models and realistic mechanisms of simple oscillators have been investigated. They all fit into the defined four classes of mechanisms : (a) 1B (e.g. Oregonator), (b) 2 (e.g. Brusselator), (c) 1X (e.g. Franck model) and (d) 1 CW (e.g. NFT mechanism). The operational methods suggested provide a way to determine an unknown mechanism, which would in principle be applicable to different kinds of chemical oscillatory systems.

Chemical waves and periodic spatial structures^{1b,d,x} :

Some chemical systems may generate travelling spatial

inhomogeneities in the concentration of intermediate species. These result from the interaction of reaction and diffusion and are referred to as reaction-diffusion waves. Gravity, electric and magnetic field can significantly affect^{1x,33j} chemical waves. A photosensitive Oregonator that has three steady states (one being stable; usual Oregonator has a single steady state) has been investigated^{33k} in a one-dimensional reaction-diffusion system to study the decomposition of chemical waves in a closed excitable medium.

The best known chemical waves appear in the Fe (phenan)₃²⁺- BrO_3^- -MA-BrMA- H_2SO_4 system in which blue waves travel in a mainly red medium. Busse^{33c} observed horizontal waves in this system when it was run in a cylinder containing a gradient of $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ along its vertical axis. These were treated as kinematic waves.

The most striking travelling waves, however, occur in a ferroin-catalyzed system run in a thin layer in a flat container such as a petri dish. If the depth of the reagent is less than the width of a travelling wave, this approximates a two-dimensional system. Such waves, called trigger waves, were first observed by Zaikin and Zhabotinskii^{33d}. Similar waves have been observed by Orban^{33e} in an uncatalyzed system. The properties of the ferroin waves in two- and three-dimensions have been reviewed by Winfree^{1e}.

The kinetic processes keep the wave profile from being increasingly smooth because of diffusion. For the kinetic processes to be effective they must be sufficiently far from equilibrium. Another necessary condition for chemical wave propagation is that the rates of the kinetic processes be non-linear functions of the descriptive variables.

There are three basic wave profiles that propagate in one spatial dimension. A *front* is an advancing transition zone that leaves the system in a different state from what it was before its passage. A *pulse* is localized in space and leaves the system as it was before its passage. Periodic or aperiodic *wavetrains* are undulatory propagating disturbances. These wavetrains can organize the reaction mixture in two- or three-dimensions into a variety of intricate, evolving patterns. The observation of Liesegang rings^{9,33h} and geochemical periodicities^{9,33b} needs mention.

The concept of chemical pattern formation through 'flow distributed oscillations' (FDO) was proposed by Kuznetsov *et al.*^{33l}. The conditions under which such patterns are formed have been determined analytically^{33m} for the Oregonator model of the B-Z reaction and confirmed by numerical computation.

Other oscillatory systems

(a) *Permanganate oscillators*³⁴ (first group of transi-

tion metal oscillators) : The first permanganate oscillator ($\text{KMnO}_4\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2\text{-H}_3\text{PO}_4$ reaction in a CSTR) was discovered by Nagy and Treindl. All members of the group consist of permanganate ions as oxidant, a reducing substrate (H_2O_2 , ninhydrin, $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, S^{2-} , SO_3^{2-} , Mn^{2+}) and phosphate ion (or AsO_4^{3-} , VO_4^{3-}) as a stabilizer for the key Mn^{IV} species.

(b) *pH oscillators*³⁵ : This is the first family of chemical oscillators that is classified according to common behavior rather than common components. Here a large change in pH is an important driving force. The first pH oscillator (1985) involves the reaction of hydrogen peroxide and sulfide ion. The major characteristics of these oscillators are well represented by the model proposed by Luo and Epstein. The first chlorite-based pH oscillator has been recently reported (2001).

(c) *Methylene blue oscillator (MBO)*³⁶ : The oscillation of methylene blue-catalyzed oxidation of HS^- by O_2 in CSTR was discovered by Burger and Field for which a mechanism was proposed by Resh *et al.*

Gas evolution oscillators (GEO)^{1f,9,37}, homogeneous gaseous oscillators^{1g,h,38}, oscillatory autoxidation of benzaldehyde^{39a}, electrochemical oscillators⁴ (mercury beating heart (MBH)^{4d,e}, oil water system^{4f}), oscillators involving sulfur chemistry^{36,39b} (dithionite decomposition^{39b}, sulfide-methylene blue system (MBO)³⁶), soda bottle oscillator^{39c}, salt-water oscillator^{39d-f}, photochemically driven oscillators^{40,17d}, oscillating chemiluminescence^{41a}, $\text{KSCN-H}_2\text{O}_2\text{-CuSO}_4\text{-NaOH}$ system^{41b}, beating polymer gels^{41c}, oscillations across artificial membranes^{41d,e} and oscillations in biological systems⁴² etc. constitute other oscillating systems.

The last one needs special mention as living organisms are open chemical systems constantly subject to external influences and invariably far from equilibrium. Rhythmic processes are characteristic of living organisms. Electrophysiological oscillations (oscillations in membrane systems) and enzymatic oscillations are quite common. Oscillatory reaction courses have been detected in numerous areas of biochemistry, in cell respiration, in carbohydrate metabolism, in enzyme synthesis, mitosis, morphogenesis, regeneration of damaged cells, and other essential life processes. The field of biochemical oscillation has been reviewed by Hess *et al.*⁴².

It remains to mention that a variety of steady and oscillatory states are possible for earth-average temperature. A simple climate model⁴³ exhibits complex behavior in global temperature.

Classification of oscillatory systems

Noyes⁹ developed a classification of oscillatory systems as follows :

(i) *Homogeneous redox oscillators* : These are driven by irreversible reduction of strong oxidants like bromate, iodate or hydrogen peroxide, e.g. B-Z, B-L and B-R systems, chlorite oscillators, permanganate oscillators etc.

(ii) *Homogeneous gaseous oscillators* : Example, oxidation of carbon monoxide.

(iii) *Interphase transport oscillators* : The transport of a gas to a liquid phase competes with the autocatalytic consumption of that gas, e.g. autoxidation of benzaldehyde.

(iv) *Phase nucleation oscillators* : These occur because of nucleation of bubbles in a supersaturated solution, e.g. gas evolution oscillators, like Morgan reaction.

(v) *Oscillators impacted by surfaces* : Oscillations in chemical composition in one phase occur because of the influence of the surface of another phase, e.g. heterogeneous catalysis of gas reactions, reactions at the surfaces of electrodes and transport through biological membranes.

Some principles responsible for oscillation

Noyes⁹ enumerated some principles responsible for oscillation and which seem to offer general utility for identifying new oscillatory systems.

(i) It is usually useful to identify the overall chemical equation which describes the net stoichiometric change in the total system. In all the common examples, at least two parallel stoichiometric paths can generate the overall change for the system as a whole, i.e.

(ii) Every elementary or pseudoelementary process takes place in the direction of decreasing free energy.

(iii) At least one stoichiometric (but not elementary) process takes place autocatalytically or with autoinhibition.

(iv) Relaxation oscillations occur when the system switches between dominance by one path and dominance by another. This constraint seems to be restricted to homogeneous redox oscillators.

(v) For homogeneous redox oscillators, one path involves only species with even numbers of electrons while another involves some species with an odd number.

(vi) A slow or delayed feedback is necessary in order to

attain repetitive transitions between states dominated by different paths.

Concluding remarks

The phenomenon of chemical oscillation is no longer a rare one. Although its history is long, the field has developed slowly because a wide variety of disciplines are involved. In fact the field has been in the focus of interest since the early seventies. Most of the chemical oscillators have been systematically designed now after the conditions that were necessary for, or conducive to oscillations were established. Temporal and spatial periodic phenomena occur at many levels of material organization from the highest level of organization (ecological) through the biological down to the molecular level, i.e. from population dynamics to chemical and biochemical reactions. Nonlinear phenomena are especially well known in biological systems and it is indisputable that biological oscillation has its origin in the chemical reactions that occur in living systems. Biological clocks and biorhythms are in many cases, easily observable and detectable; to these belong the transmission of nerve impulses, propagation of brain waves, circadian rhythms etc. At the biochemical level of organization, glycolytic oscillations are the most thoroughly studied oscillations. Anyway the area of research is undoubtedly an exciting one and is being extensively explored at present both by theoreticians and experimentalists.

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